

BALANCE IN EXCHANGE: ADAM SMITH'S THIRD KIND OF JUSTICE

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ABSTRACT

Two kinds of justice are usually recognized in Adam Smith's thought, commutative and distributive. These two principles do not account for the terms of exchange in *The Wealth of Nations*, since they are a matter of not stealing or making presents. However, Smith also envisages a third, often overlooked, sense of justice. This is a matter of just evaluation of something's worth. The article argues that this third kind of justice can describe Smith's exchange when people balance the respective interests they have in seeing the esteem they deserve rightly recognised. This implies that equality among traders has not to be understood only as the preliminary condition of exchange, but can also be seen as its outcome.

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Justice has a central role in Smith's thought, yet it is usually seen as absent from exchange in *The Wealth of Nations* (WN I.ii). This article argues, instead, that the concept of just evaluation of deserved esteem can provide an understanding of Smith's exchange, which also establishes relations of equality among traders.

Scholars have discussed Smith's approach to justice in depth, especially focusing on the two traditional kinds of justice, commutative and distributive (see, among others, Haakonssen 1981, Brown 1994, Young and Gordon 1996, Witztum 1997, Griswold 1999, Salter 2000, Verburg 2000, Raphael 2001, Fleischacker 1999, 2004a, 2004b, Forman-Barzilai 2010, Vivenza 2001, 2010). When Smith addresses them in TMS, he describes commutative justice as a matter of avoiding injury to others and the distributive as proper beneficence. In the former case, it can be a matter of not stealing, not cheating and respecting contracts, in the latter of generosity and making presents. Neither of these kinds of justice enters into the determination of the terms of exchange (the exchange *ratio*). The terms of exchange can be enforced by commutative justice when they are not respected, but they cannot be fixed by it (e.g. as compensation for some injury due to failure to recover costs, see Salter 1997, Young 1997b, Walraevens 2014). Commutative justice can only imply the absence of coercion as preliminary condition of exchange, the absence of fraud and the respect for agreement reached in exchange (see Young 1997a, Salter 1997, Rothschild 2001, Darwall 2004, 2006, Fleischacker 2004a, Brown 2016). Nor can distributive justice describe terms of exchange, for

Smith sees it as having to do with generosity and charity (for discussion of the long debate on the role of distributive justice in Smith, see among others Brown 1997, Verburg 2000, Rothschild 2001, Fleischacker 2004b, Vivenza 2010, Herzog 2014, Smith 2014). From this point of view, the equivalence that results between benefits exchanged cannot be but the fruit of bargaining between parties that do not impose on one another while pursuing their own personal interest. In its extended meaning, the pursuit of one's personal interest means that people can take into account the interest of everyone except the interest of the other party to the exchange (see Wicksteed 1910, Brown 1994, Fleischacker 2004a, Heath 2013), apart in order to adopt a strategy for reaching an agreement (see Fontaine 1997, Fleischacker 2004a, Dellemotte 2005, Walraevens 2010), or to avoid harming the other party's interest by moderating their own desires through self-command (see Young 1997a, Witztum 1998, Griswold 1999, Darwall 2004, Paganelli 2010). In the determination of the content of their bargain, these parties are neither unjust nor just from the point of view of commutative or distributive justice; they do not refer to either of these two senses of justice in their evaluations, apart the minimal respect of property and individual freedom.

However, Smith introduces a further and largely overlooked sense of justice to explain Plato's account of the nature of virtue in the opening of Part VII of TMS. This is the last part of TMS, but, according to the editors of the Glasgow edition, it seems likely that Smith began his lectures on ethics from this part.¹ The distinction between the two traditional kinds of justice and a third concept of justice, therefore, is not an irrelevant issue if Smith decided to address it at the beginning of his ethics lessons on which TMS is based. Here, Smith clarifies that when,

¹ In the first note to Part VII of TMS, the editors of the Glasgow edition write that: 'it seems likely that the first version of Smith's lectures on ethics began at this point, with a systematic survey of earlier theories before developing Smith's own views' (SMITH 1976b: 265; see also RAPHAEL 2007: 9–10). The comparison with other systems, placed at the end of TMS probably for editorial reasons, was thus originally intended to open Smith's lectures, probably for pedagogical reasons. On the structure of TMS, see also BEE (2021b).

in TMS, he uses the word «justice» alone, he is referring to commutative justice; whereas, he is referring to distributive justice when in TMS he addresses «proper beneficence» and to Plato's justice when he addresses in TMS «the exact and perfect propriety of conduct and behaviour» (see TMS VII.ii.1.10). Few scholars recognise the presence of this last, third sense of justice in TMS, but focus on the other two kinds (see Salter 1994, Griswold 1999, Fleischacker 2004a, Raphael 2007, Smith 2014); more specifically, Jeffrey Young (1997a) associates it with the duties of individuals towards the community, while Daniel Klein (2021) argues that it «looms large in matters determined by the jural 'superior,' that is, the governor». Here, instead, this third kind of justice is understood as the more general «just evaluation» of the worth of something or someone by any impartial spectator.

This article shows in which sense, according to Smith, the third concept of justice «comprehends» the offices of both distributive and commutative justice (proper beneficence and proper punishment), and it is also «more extensive» than either of them; in this sense it can be seen as a more general concept of justice, since it explains the other two kinds while also extending beyond them. Just evaluation is needed for proper punishment and proper beneficence, but it can be claimed only when it can be identified fairly precisely, as in the case of the minimal respect of propriety and reputation. Just evaluation cannot be claimed in what exceeds this precise minimal respect, but this does not imply that it cannot be desired. To desire the praise that is really due to us, even if it cannot be claimed, for Smith is to desire no more than «a most essential act of justice» (TMS III.2.8, see also Schwarze and Scott 2015).

Smith does not just say «act of justice», since in TMS he uses «justice» alone to refer to commutative justice, but he adds that it is a «most essential» act of justice. He is referring here to natural justice. For Smith, natural justice is the basis of positive law (see Haaknossen 1981, 136-9; Griswold 1999, 256) but is not reduced to it. It also includes distributive justice as well as this desire to obtain the praise that is really due to us. In the section on the three kinds of

justice, Smith explicitly refers to natural justice using Grotius' terms of *justitia expletrix* and *justitia attributix* to explain commutative and distributive justice through his theory of moral sentiments based on the impartial spectator (see TMS VII.ii.1.10). Smith explains these kinds of natural justice with the capacity to judge adequately according to the impartial spectator, that is, through just evaluation.² Since this third kind of justice comprehends the other two kinds and exceeds them, it could take into account what is considered to lie outside commutative and distributive justice, such as the determination of terms of exchange.

Smith's readers have focused mainly on the bipolarity between commutative and distributive justice probably because these are the two kinds of justice traditionally studied from Aristotle onwards, not least because the Aristotelian tradition has usually overlooked the fact that there is a third sense of justice also in Aristotle (see Giuliani 1970, 726; Azzoni 2006, 43). This article shows the possible link between Aristotle's third kind of justice and the third kind of justice in Smith – who seems to have been a close reader of Aristotle – and how both of these third kinds of justice are linked to exchange.³

² On the principles of natural justice in Smith as arising from the impartial spectator's sense of justice, see also GRISWOLD (1999, 256), who, however, also states that Smith never followed through on his project to write a theory of jurisprudence because he would have been faced with the impossibility of accounting for «a final and comprehensive philosophical system articulating the "general principles of law and government"» on the basis of his theory of moral sentiments (1999, 256-9). It would be beyond the scope of this article to discuss this or indeed any other explanations that differ from that given by Smith himself shortly before his death in the Advertisement added to the last edition of the TMS in 1790, namely lack of time due to the same occupations that had long precluded him from making that last revision of the TMS.

³ STEWART 1980 [1795] recalls that Smith had a reputation for his refined discussions on Greek etymology, which suggests that he probably read Aristotle directly in Greek. This is further borne out by the fact that he possessed a complete edition of the works of Aristotle in Greek and Latin (see BONAR 1894, MIZUTA 2000), in which his notes on justice were found (see «Manuscript Fragment on Justice» in Appendix II of the Glasgow edition of TMS).

The hypothesis explored in this article is that just evaluation can have a role in exchange when people desire just recognition of their deserved praise. Exchange in WN can be seen not only as based on the pursuit of one's own personal interest, but also as based on the balance of respective interests people have in seeing respective deserved praises justly recognised. The motive of this kind of exchange is the desire to reach the agreed equivalence that reveals this mutual and just recognition. This article shows that the concept of just evaluation of deserved praise can be consistent with this reading of exchange in WN, and it can explain the determinations of the terms of exchange. Accordingly, equality among traders has not only to be seen as the preliminary condition of exchange (as in Young 1997a, Rothschild 2001, Darwall 2004, 2006, Fleischacker 2004a), but also – as a rereading of the Aristotelian conception of exchange in terms of Smithian theory similarly shows – as the result of exchange based on just evaluation.

JUST EVALUATION COMPREHENDS THE OFFICES OF BOTH COMMUTATIVE AND DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE

In TMS, Smith makes a distinction between commutative and distributive justice, stating that the former is a matter of not injuring others, while the latter consists in proper beneficence (see TMS VII.ii.1). Yet, having defined them, Smith points out that there is a third sense in which we can be said to be unjust. This concept has so far received scant attention from scholars. It is therefore worth looking into it, examining all its various aspects and seeing how it relates with the two traditional ideas of justice. In particular, this section explores how it «comprehends in it» the offices of both these kind of justice (TMS VII.ii.1.10), by showing its relationship with the judgement of the impartial spectator.⁴

⁴ By the concept of «impartial spectator» Smith addresses how we can judge impartially the others and ourselves; on this concept, see among others HAAKONSEN (1981), GRISWOLD (1999), RAPHAEL (2007).

This other «sense in which the word justice is sometimes taken», Smith writes, runs «through all languages» (TMS VII.ii.1.10, emphasis added). The point he means to stress here is that, as in the case of the other two senses with which it is naturally connected, this third sense also has to do with the natural sentiments of human beings. Smith points out this affinity thus: «The word, it is to be observed, which expresses justice in the Greek language, has *several different meanings*; and as the correspondent word *in all other languages*, so far as I know, *has the same*, there must be some *natural affinity* among those various significations». (TMS VII.ii.1.10, emphasis added).

Smith introduces this third sense in the course of trying to make sense of Platonic «justice». As can be seen from the following description, it consists in giving everything its proper place, that is just evaluation by the impartial spectator:

It is in this last sense that we are said to be unjust, when we do not seem *to value any particular object with that degree of esteem*, or to pursue it with that degree of ardour *which to the impartial spectator it may appear to deserve* or to be naturally fitted for exciting (TMS VII.ii.1.10, emphasis added).

According to this third sense, we are said to do injustice towards a poem or a picture when, for example, our admiration is «not [...] enough», or when we do rather more than justice to it, and our admiration is «too much» (TMS VII.ii.1.10). We are said to be unjust towards ourselves when we appear «not to give sufficient attention to any particular object of self-interest» (TMS VII.ii.1.1), as well as we can be unjust towards the others when this attention is excessive. Instead, we evaluate fairly when we attribute neither more nor less worth than each object of judgement deserves, according to the esteem of that «third person» who is the impartial spectator (Cf. TMS III.3.3). In this article, the sense of justice associated with Plato is

addressed with the concept of «just evaluation» – that is, the evaluation of worth that any impartial spectator can approve – and not the terms «evaluative justice» or «estimative justice» (as in Klein 2021), to avoid misunderstanding about the meaning of the word «justice» in Smith’s thought, mainly relating to commutative justice (see Griswold 1999, Vivenza 2001, Fleischacker 2004a).⁵ Since just evaluation is needed by everyone to pursue even the object of self-interest, it cannot be something related only to wise people. It is in this sense that we can read what Smith says when he writes that, in this third sense, «what is called justice means the same thing with exact and perfect propriety of conduct and behaviour» (TMS VII.ii.1.10).⁶ Smith writes «exact and perfect propriety», but this does not mean that we need to be far more virtuous than ordinary people when we evaluate an object fairly, but simply that our conduct can be perfectly appropriate in that precise moment according to any impartial spectator.⁷

For this reason, it «comprehends» within itself «the offices of both commutative and distributive justice» – proper punishment (e. g. for theft) and proper beneficence (e. g. by gifts) – as well as of every other virtue (TMS VII.ii.1.10). If we evaluate properly and act accordingly, then we are beneficent in the right way and avoid injuring the others.⁸

⁵ See also FLEISCHACKER (2004a, 148), who distinguishes between «political justice» (i.e. justice enforced by law or commutative justice) and «moral justice» (justice more broadly conceived), arguing that «Smith carves the former out of the latter».

⁶ Smith writes that «the account given by Plato of the nature of virtue [...], it is evident, coincides in every respect» with what he wrote in TMS about «the propriety of conduct» (TMS V.ii.1.11).

⁷ As Smith explains in the first Part of TMS devoted to propriety of conduct: «Upon many occasions, to act with the most perfect propriety, requires no more than that common and ordinary degree of sensibility or self-command which the most worthless of mankind are possess of, and sometimes even that degree is not necessary» (I.i.5.7).

⁸ Since people could avoid harming others by simply observing positive law, there would be no need here to bring into play the third kind of justice, that is, the evaluation that any impartial spectator would consider appropriate. Positive law, however, can be seen in Smith’s thought as emerging from natural rules of justice and thus arising from the impartial spectator’s sense of justice (see HAAKONSEN

Smith states that this just evaluation is «very much a-kin» to distributive justice (TMS VII.ii.1.10), for the latter, too, consists in due recognition of worth (see also Raphael 2007, 75), but distributive justice occurs in the relationship others have with us and entails consequent action.⁹ From the point of view of distributive justice, «we are said not to do justice to our neighbour unless we conceive for him all that love, respect, and esteem, which his character, his situation, and *his connexion with ourselves*, render suitable and proper for us to feel, and *unless we act accordingly*» (TMS VII.ii.1.10, emphasis added).

Smith makes it clear that he does not take distributive justice in quite the same sense as Aristotle, according to whom, he points out, «it consists in the proper distribution of rewards from the public stock of a community» (TMS VII.ii.1.10). Nevertheless, Smith retains the sense, applying it to our relationship with our neighbour: «It is in this sense that we are said to do injustice to *a man of merit* who is connected with us, though we abstain from hurting him in every respect, if we do not exert ourselves to serve him and to place him in that situation in which *the impartial spectator* would be pleased to see him» (TMS VII.ii.1.10, emphasis added). Beneficence is not *just* in itself, for the need is to act in conformity with «*proper beneficence*» (TMS VII.ii.1.10, emphasis added). It is in this way that Smith states that distributive justice consists «in the becoming use of what is our own, and in the applying it to those purposes either of charity or generosity» (TMS VII.ii.1.10). The recent debate on distributive justice and the alleged «right» of the poor to be helped often risks shifting Smith's sense of distributive justice in the direction of the more recent meaning, namely the redistribution of goods (for an accurate explanation of distributive justice in Smith, see Fleischacker 2004b, Vivenza 2010).

1981, 136-9; GRISWOLD 1999, 256), although «in no country do the decisions of positive law coincide exactly, in every case, with the rules which the natural sense of justice would dictate», which is why systems of positive laws «can never be regarded as accurate systems of the rules of natural justice» (TMS VII.iv.36).

⁹ Just evaluation is in general «very much a-kin» to distributive justice, as we will shortly see, also in relationship to the exactness of the rules of judgment.

Redistribution of goods has to do with the government exacting taxes from citizens with the aim of reducing social inequalities, in particular through aid to the poorest. However, this legal imposition is not directly connected with the moral obligation which Smith usually refers to, and which, as already seen, is by contrast a matter of generosity and free donation of one's own resources. The beneficence Smith refers to in connection with distributive justice is «proper» when we impartially consider the others' merit, taking into account their situation vis-à-vis our own, implying that distributive justice must look to just evaluation in order to be operative.¹⁰

Like beneficence, injury, too, needs just evaluation. According to Smith, it comes within the sphere of commutative rather than distributive justice. The commutative justice that Smith refers to is the justice that Aristotle calls «corrective», and concerns the criminal domain rather than the civil world of contracts and suchlike (see Vivenza 2010, 52). Describing commutative justice, Smith explains that injury is not simply a matter of hurting others, but of doing so for motives that the impartial spectator disapproves of: «This virtue is justice: the violation of justice is injury: it does real and positive hurt to some particular persons, *from motives which are naturally disapproved of*. It is, therefore, the proper object of resentment, and of punishment, which is the natural consequence of resentment» (TMS II.ii.1.5, emphasis added).¹¹

As beneficence is not sufficient in order to be just, so hurting others is not in itself unjust. There may be «proper motives» driving us to hurt others – motives that any impartial

¹⁰ In the «Manuscript Fragment on Justice», Smith explains: «When we chuse [-?](r)ather, for example, to do a good Office to a new acquaintance than to an Old friend we are said to do Injustice to the latter» (see Appendix II of the Glasgow edition of TMS, 390).

¹¹ In the LJ, Smith says that «we may conceive an injury was done when an impartial spectator would be of opinion he was injured» (LJ A i.36). See also TMS (VII.4.8). On commutative justice and the impartial spectator, see also SALTER (1997, 678–81), OTTESON (2017, 127).

spectator would approve of without resentment.¹² Resentment is appropriate when just indignation arises over some hurt being done for improper motives. Punishment is deserved only when performed against a «*proper* object of resentment» (TMS II.ii.1.5, emphasis added). Legitimate defence, for example, is a proper motive that can lead us to hurt another without deserving punishment (see LJ A, ii.114).¹³ Rather, this aspect of commutative justice is useful here for us to see that not only distributive but also commutative justice must look to just evaluation in order to be effectively applied, since both of them require the judgement of the impartial spectator. Distributive or commutative justice can be effectively applied in the form of just reward or just punishment when the impartial spectator judges the propriety of motives for actions.

JUST EVALUATION IS MORE EXTENSIVE THAN DISTRIBUTIVE AND COMMUTATIVE JUSTICE

In order to examine the relationship between just evaluation and the two traditional kinds of justice, we need to consider the way the former comes into play in weighing up the motives for actions. The impartial spectator deems them proper or improper on the basis of the evaluations that lie behind them: improper actions derive from improper evaluations, proper actions from proper evaluations. Smith makes this clear in a passage in the *Lectures of*

¹² For example, there is the indignation we feel against another person who has hurt someone unjustly, and the corresponding desire to punish this person for it: «there can be no *proper motive* for hurting our neighbour, there can be no incitement to do evil to another, which mankind will go along with, *except* just indignation for evil which that other has done to us» (II.ii.2.1, emphasis added).

¹³ Evaluating the legitimacy of such defence implies, to begin with, evaluating the motives that drove the wrongdoer, provoking defensive action, so as to ascertain whether there is actual injury and then, in the second place, evaluating the defensive action taken in relation to the injury received. It is on this aspect of commutative justice that SALTER (1997) focuses to criticize the correspondence that YOUNG (1986) draws between injury and costs incurred.

Jurisprudence (LJ) where he distinguishes between perfect and imperfect rights, or in other words between rights which can be imposed and rights that cannot be claimed. Smith reinterprets this distinction from the jurisprudential tradition – referring explicitly to Hutcheson and Pufendorf (see LJ A i.14) – through his idea of the impartial spectator (see also Haakonssen 1981, 99-100; Pesciarelli 1988, 90-1).¹⁴ This distinction has been analysed from the perspective of commutative and distributive justice (see, among others, Haakonssen 1981, Witztum 1997, Verburg 2000, Vivenza 2010, Salter 2012). Here it is further explored from the point of view of just evaluation. In particular, this section investigates how according to Smith just evaluation applies to a «more extensive» domain than that of distributive and commutative justice: it comprehends their offices, but it also helps account for just recognition of worth, which does not necessarily imply either of them (TMS VII.ii.1.10).

In the LJ Smith discusses the difference between perfect and imperfect rights with regard to the right of a person «to an unspoiled character» and «to what he possesses», that is, not to be injured «in his reputation» or «in his estate» (LJ A i.12).

A man's reputation, Smith explains, may be attacked «when one endeavours to bring his character below what is the common standard amongst men» (LJ A i.13). He states that practically all men, «perhaps 99 of 100», deserve better treatment (LJ A i.13-14). Someone who attacks the reputation of a person belonging to this vast majority in this way is unjust from the point of view of just evaluation: he certainly fails to show «enough» esteem for the character of the other person. In this way, he injures him, unjustly hurting him «either by falsely representing him as a proper object of resentment or punishment as by calling him a thief or robber, or *by depreciating his real worth*» (LJ B 7, emphasis added). The injured party may respond with due resentment, calling for just punishment with reparation of the injury. Since it can be claimed, the right to an unspoiled character is a «perfect right». Hence just

¹⁴ On the connection between Smith and the natural law tradition, see FORBES (1982), CREMASCHI (2002), VIVENZA (2008).

evaluation entails commutative justice, which can impose respect of this right by force, and can thus be enforced by the law. On the other hand, if some people were to do «more than justice» to some other persons' reputation, we might say that, to the eyes of any impartial spectator, they are flattering them (on Smith's criticism of flattery, see TMS VII.ii.4).¹⁵

Between defamation and flattery there is, however, just recognition of the others' worth. Nevertheless, the lowest limit of reputation to be recognised to anyone can be identified fairly precisely, being applicable to the vast majority of human beings. Instead, exact evaluation of the reputation of each individual that exceeds the minimal respect calls for more sensitive response, which cannot be subject to precise, predetermined rules. The minimum respect owed to anyone may belong to the grammar of social life,¹⁶ but there can be no precise rule to establish whether «Mr. Pope was no better poet than the ordinary ones of his own time» (LJ B 7).

Thus, while defaming no one we might still be unjust from the point of view of just evaluation in judging someone's reputation. However, there being no precise rules, no such evaluation can be expected. A shortcoming from this point of view cannot entail actual injury, and so does not imply commutative justice: «We do not however injure a man when we do not give him *all the praise* that is due to his merit» (LJ B 7, emphasis added). What we are dealing with here, then, is an «imperfect right". Nevertheless, it is a right, since it is reprehensible that we do not receive all the praise that is due to us. At the same time, it is imperfect, since we cannot require it to be respected. In this case, just evaluation can only be preferable from a moral point of view, but it does not give rise to commutative justice. This does not mean that an

¹⁵ Although different from it, this reading is not incompatible with the interpretation offered by WITZTUM (1997) on the difference in degree between commutative and distributive justice.

¹⁶ On the parallel between the rules of justice and the rules of grammar, see TMS (VII.iv.1); see also VIVENZA (2010, 52), OTTESON (2017). On the precision of rules of justice in Smith's thought, see FLEISCHACKER (2004a, 153–76).

exact evaluation of worth that exceeds the minimal respect cannot be reached, but only that it cannot be claimed and imposed by force. On the other hand, when it becomes an occasion for just recompense, it gives rise to distributive justice.

The distinction between perfect and imperfect rights includes the right of people to their estate (LJ A i.12). It, too, can be interpreted from the point of view of the relationship between just evaluation and the two traditional kinds of justice. It is the right to one's own estate which, according to Smith, in a primitive state «would extend no farther than possession» (LJ A i.44). Failure to respect it provokes resentment in the impartial spectator, and the proper punishment and compensation for the injury can be imposed by force. The right to what one possesses is a perfect right and comes under the jurisdiction of commutative justice (LJ A i.15). As we have seen, according to the concept of just evaluation «we are said to be unjust, when we do not seem to value any particular object with that degree of esteem, or *to pursue it with that degree of ardour which to the impartial spectator it may appear to deserve or to be naturally fitted for exciting*» (TMS VII.ii.1.10, emphasis added). Any impartial spectator would react with antipathy towards someone who desires things belonging to others too much, without showing the least concern for the others, and so going in improper pursuit of the objects. On the other hand, we might say that people who went on letting what they have in their hands be taken from them without ever reacting, or squandered everything they possessed, would be considered by any impartial spectator unjust towards themselves from the point of view of just evaluation. They would not be desiring with the just degree of ardour what it is proper for anyone to desire, when one esteems oneself impartially (see TMS VII.ii.1.10, see also TMS I.ii.3.3).

Between theft and waste lies just evaluation of what we have. However, as in the case of reputation, we cannot expect others to value what we possess with the exact degree of evaluation it deserves. The claim that something in our possession cannot be taken from us

without proper motives can be acknowledged unambiguously and take its place among the rules of the grammar of social life. As in the case of reputation, however, there can be no precise rules for the just evaluation of what we possess or what we have done that exceeds the minimal respect. A poem may be written with perfectly correct grammar, Smith points out, but there are no precise rules to evaluate its elegance (see TMS VII.iv.1). An inexact evaluation from others of what we possess cannot be punished by commutative justice as long as it does not injure us, for example, opening the way to theft. Their just evaluation of our possessions can only be desired inasmuch as it is morally preferable. On the other hand, when it becomes an occasion for just reward, it gives rise to generosity. As already seen, just evaluation comprehends the offices of both commutative and distributive justice (for example, proper punishment or proper beneficence), but it is also more extensive than either of them: for example, it can be a matter of just recognition of worth, which does not imply punishment for theft, nor indeed generous giving.

Theft relates to commutative justice while giving concerns distributive justice. Interdiction of theft can be imposed, but no one can be obliged to be generous (see TMS II.ii.1.7). Differing, however, from both theft and giving, there is exchange. Law cannot impose the just evaluation of worth that exceeds the minimal respect of our own reputation or possession, but it can be desired. The hypothesis we advance here is that exchange could be also based on this desire and thus interpreted through just evaluation in what exceeds the domain of the two traditional kinds of justice.

JUST EVALUATION IN EXCHANGE

The terms of exchange cannot be described through reference to the two traditional kinds of justice. Distributive justice does not describe them, for Smith sees it as having to do with

generosity and charity. Commutative justice can describe the mutual respect as precondition of exchange that avoids domination, cheating and theft (see Young 1997a, Rothschild 2001, Darwall 2004, 2006, Fleischacker 2004a, Brown 2016) as well as respect for the agreement reached in exchange (see Salter 1997), but cannot explain its terms (the exchange *ratio*). Young (1986, 1995, 1997a) tried to explain the terms of exchange through commutative justice. According to him, for Smith property should be attributed to each according to the costs incurred. This implies that a fair exchange price should compensate for such costs. Otherwise, there would be damage to property and commutative justice should come into play to repair the damage. From this point of view, the natural price is the price that any impartial spectator would judge fair considering the costs incurred. A price that would not remunerate such costs would constitute an injury to the other exchanger's property and commutative justice could impose a fairer price. Salter (1994, 1997), however, pointed out that if no one hurts anyone for an improper motive, as in the case of exchange based on reciprocal agreement, then no punishment is deserved and so there can be no injury to be compensated for.¹⁷ This point led Young to circumscribe his hypothesis, observing that "natural price has *normative* significance for Smith", for example when he criticises monopoly and the mercantilist system (1997b, 686–88, emphasis added). In this way, however, the possibility to *describe* exchange as conceived by Smith through a form of justice is excluded.¹⁸

¹⁷ See also WITZTUM (1997), SALTER (2000), VERBURG (2000). On this debate and the importance of the system of natural liberty and free competition for the emergence of the natural price as the just price, see WALRAEVENS (2014).

¹⁸ Commutative justice can also be seen as that imperative of economic ethics which requires giving everyone his or her due, in the sense of bringing the actual price into line with the price prevailing in the given economy (see KOSLOWSKI 2001, 186-9). This idea of commutative justice in exchange does not seem to be present in Smith's thought. As we intend to show here, however, with the third justice we can account for the formation of the prevailing price in the market as explained in the WN.

In this section, the possibility of describing the terms of exchange through the third concept of justice is explored.

If we cannot claim all the praise that is due to us, we can at least desire it: «To *desire* it where it is really due, is to *desire* no more than that a most essential act of *justice* should be done to us» (TMS III.2.8, emphasis added; see also Schwarze and Scott 2015, 473). As Smith sees it, obtaining from others the esteem we believe we deserve constitutes «perhaps, the strongest of all our desires» (TMS VI.i.3).

One way to obtain the appreciation we believe we deserve is to obtain just evaluation of our «good offices» (WN I.ii.2-3), which are the benefits – goods or services – that we provide to others. However, we cannot rely on the other’s benevolence if we really want to obtain it: the rules that apply to gratitude and generosity are «vague and indeterminate» (TMS III.6.9). Your gratitude, Smith observes, need not necessarily correspond precisely to the value of the good offices received from another, because it must take into account «the difference between his character and yours, between his circumstances and yours» (TMS III.6.9). It is precisely for this reason that gratitude and generosity come within the sphere of distributive justice, which takes into account the various different characters and situations.¹⁹ This means that the reward might come about at a time and in a way that do not correspond exactly to the value of the good offices it returns. Smith states this explicitly, speaking of the rules of gratitude: «That as soon as we can we should make a return of equal, and if possible of superior value to the services we have received, would seem to be a pretty plain rule, and one which admitted of scarce any exceptions. Upon the most superficial examination, however, this rule will appear

¹⁹ Having said that we are just from the point of view of distributive justice if we appraise our neighbour in the way that «*his character, his situation, and his connexion with ourselves, render suitable and proper for us to feel*», Smith writes that distributive justice «consists in proper beneficence, in the becoming use of what is our own, and in the applying it to those purposes either of charity or generosity, to which it is most suitable, *in our situation*, that it should be applied» (TMS VII.ii.1.10, emphasis added).

to be in the highest degree loose and inaccurate, and to admit of ten thousand exceptions» (TMS III.6.9).

Following the rule of gratitude, the return should if possible be of superior value (and so not even necessarily of equal value), and in any case there are too many exceptions to a rule that appears to be highly imprecise. Moreover, we cannot demand that someone be grateful for our generosity, proper as it may be. Exacting gratitude by force would be even more improper than lack of gratitude (see TMS II.ii.1.3). Yet, we can always show to others our desire of just recognition by not offering our good offices when we think that the others fail to rightly recognise their worth. This right recognition, instead, can be *revealed* by what the others are disposed to offer us in exchange.

Exchange can thus be a way to satisfy perhaps even the strongest of our desires. When others offer us something in exchange, they are revealing that they consider our services to be worth as much as theirs. Through this comparison we can explicitly know how much they esteem us for having performed those services. In this sense, when others esteem the worth of our good offices equivalent to theirs, which we also esteem equivalent to ours, then both parties consider their reciprocal good offices justly evaluated and find in the appreciations of others confirmation of their own evaluations.

If I am a brewer and people mostly prefer the beer of other brewers, I would probably be discouraged from continuing since I do not find confirmation of my own self-evaluation in their appreciation. On the other hand, if my clients are willing to pay even more for my beer than for other beers, it is a sign that they truly appreciate my skill. For their part, my clients show me that they are not beggars and that they deserve that beer because the services they provided to someone else were appreciated enough to allow them to buy my beer. When they negotiate their money for that beer, they implicitly propose or accept an equivalence between the deserved approval they received for the services they provided to others (revealed by that

amount of money) and the approval that they bestow me for that beer. If they do not buy that beer directly from me but in a pub, it does not imply that exchange could not work in the way described here. The fact that they often go to that pub to buy that beer might mean that they appreciate not only how the beer is brewed but also how it is distributed (assuming, of course, the absence of monopolistic positions). Exchange, therefore, could take this form both for sellers and buyers, including when the buyers offer nothing but money for services that the sellers may not even have produced themselves.²⁰

We might not immediately agree with the others on their evaluation. As already seen in the previous sections, for Smith there are no precise rules to determine the exact value of something or someone beyond the minimal respect of reputation or property. With regard to exchange, in WN (I.v.4) he observes that «it is often difficult to ascertain the proportion between two different quantities of labour. The time spent in two different sorts of work will not always alone determine this proportion. The different degrees of hardship endured, and of ingenuity exercised, must likewise be taken into account». And he adds: «it is not easy to find any accurate measure either of hardship or ingenuity» (ibid.). Thus, we could not agree on evaluation of our reciprocal good offices, holding that the others do not value our good office «enough», or value their own «too much». In this case, the «higgling and bargaining» begins (WN I.v.4). Each of us tries to persuade the others of what we consider the just evaluation of whatever might be the object of exchange. From this perspective, exchange would not be a means to impose on others, in the sense of persuading others to give us what we want by simulating an interest in what they want (as in Force 2003, 130–32; Rasmussen 2008, 79; Walraevens 2010, 17; Griswold 2018, 204). Exchange would not be sought only for the pleasure of having persuaded the others (as in Young 1997a, Dellemotte 2005,

²⁰ If the motive for exchange is the desire for deserved approval, there can be no point in acting unfairly, even with strangers (as instead in VINER [1972] 2015, 80–2).

Walraevens 2010), but for the pleasure of having persuaded the others that we really deserve their approval, and thus for the pleasure of having obtained their deserved esteem.

Since for Smith there are no precise rules for evaluating the real worth of something, the terms of exchange can be more or less exact in confirming our deserved praises, and more or less similar to the terms of similar exchanges. If the rules for determining prices were as precise as «the rules of grammar» (as, for Smith, in the case of corrective justice, see TMS VII.iv.1), then there would be no room for any kind of discussion, and prices could be fixed independently of market negotiations, for example by the government. But this can hardly be seen as the way Smith explains the determination of prices. Although these prices are not necessarily identical for similar services or goods (since no «accurate measure» exists to evaluate different kinds of labour), being the outcome of impartial judgements, they will approximate one another «according to that sort of rough equality which, though not exact, is sufficient for carrying on the business of common life» (WN I.v.4). This means that, when there is no excess of demand or supply in the market, the higgling and bargaining can give rise to agreed judgements and thus to similar prices for similar services at a certain «time and place» (WN I.vii.3), from which the natural price emerges. As Smith explains: “When the quantity brought to market is just sufficient to supply the effectual demand and no more, the market price naturally comes to be either exactly, or as nearly as can be judged of, the same with the natural price” (WN I.vii.11; emphasis added). The “effectual demand” is the demand of “those who are willing to pay the natural price,” that is—following the reading proposed here—the demand of those who are willing to recognize the praise deserved for “raising, preparing, and bringing” the commodities to market, thereby paying rent and wages and making provision for profit at their natural rates. For Smith the mechanism of supply and effective demand has no effect on determining the natural price. The only effect of this mechanism lies in bringing the market price back to the natural price when the quantity

supplied in the market is not quite enough to satisfy the effective demand. If the mechanism of supply and demand works in order to bring the actual price around the natural price, the natural price is not established by the supply and demand mechanism, but by ‘higgling and bargaining’. The ‘higgling and bargaining’ can be seen as the result of a general consensus at a certain time and place that emerges from various negotiations approximating a similar price for similar services.²¹ According to Jeffrey Young, ‘the natural price will be a consensus price which individuals and the spectator will view as fair in the sense of not causing injury to any party. [...] Smith grounds exchange value on a spectator-approved social consensus in the same way he grounds justice and morality in general. This consensus is arrived at through the “higgling and bargaining” (Young 1986, pp. 375–376).²² In the exchange suggested here, people do not refer to the impartial spectator only out of respect for their property (and thus possibly also for corrective justice, see Young 1986, 1997), but primarily for the deliberate purpose of recognizing the praise deserved by both parties as a way to achieve the equivalence that satisfies the common desire for deserved esteem. In this ‘higgling and bargaining’ we can find confirmation that the others are indeed truly persuaded that we deserve the praise they bestow on us.

If we cannot come to an agreement, then the exchange could not take place.²³ This can also be the result of self-deceit, leading one or both exchangers to overvalue themselves, failing to pay correct heed to the evaluation our imaginary impartial spectator makes of us (see TMS III.4, see also Darwall 1988, Pack 1991, Gerschlager 2001, 2002, Fleischacker 2011, Walraevens

²¹ On the social rules representing the consensus emerging in society at a certain time and place as a result of a number of impartial judgments in specific situations, see BROWN (2016).

²² For certain similarities between Hutcheson’s considerations on price and Smith’s natural price as determined by what the impartial spectator sees as the ‘fair price’ considering all the expenses and risks incurred, see PESCIARELLI (1988, 148-53).

²³ Circumstances can bring us to exchange even if we do not consider the other’s evaluation of our object of exchange really just.

2019). When, on the other hand, each, judging impartially, concurs that what is offered by the others corresponds in value to what is given in exchange, then we have exchange such that both parties are left satisfied with confirmation of their evaluations. In this case, on reaching agreement the exchangers recognise that the worth of their good offices are valued neither too little nor too much, given the circumstances in which they find themselves. Mutual agreement is fundamental for exchange based on the desire of deserved approval, because real confirmation of our own self-assessment through exchange can be obtained only if we are convinced that the others are judging freely and impartially. If their appreciation were imposed, there would be no such confirmation on their part. From this point of view, the just evaluation that could be sought in exchange can only be desired, and thus constitute the motive for exchange, but there is no sense in imposing it by force or law (as, instead, in the case of commutative justice determining the content of exchange, see Young 1986). We can thus assume a possible role for just evaluation in exchange through right equalization of respective deserved praises. Young's hypothesis (1986) that the evaluation of the impartial spectator plays a part in exchange can, then, be maintained without bringing in the correspondence between costs and injury, and thus commutative justice, as he does.

Of course, this does not imply that exchange always happens in this form, but that exchange *can* take this form when people seek above all deserved approval. People can also be moved by vanity, such as merchants building an empire for their own benefit. But this is not necessarily the only motive for exchange, and perhaps not even the most representative, which Smith, by contrast, sees in the desire for deserved approval.²⁴ According to him, simply obtaining the praise of others without believing oneself worthy of it is generally unsatisfactory, as is knowing oneself worthy through the judgement of one's impartial

²⁴ In commercial society the motive for exchange can be vanity, but with exchange based on deserved praise we can account for the propensity to exchange, which Smith saw lying behind the process leading to commercial society, as explained in BEE (2021a, 131-5).

spectator without obtaining the praise of others (see TMS VII.ii.4.10). On the other hand, obtaining the praise of others when one believes oneself to be worthy of it – that is, obtaining the deserved praise of others – is what gives us the greatest satisfaction. This is because for Smith the others' approval “necessarily confirms our own self-approbation” (TMS III.2.3; see also TMS VI.i.3; see also Bee 2021a, 121-3). From this perspective, the exchange based on the desire for deserved approval may be the type that satisfies us most, and therefore that we desire most.

If the interest of both parties lies in obtaining from others confirmation of the worth of our good offices, then the motive of exchange is precisely to find the equivalence that reveals agreement on the mutual recognition of that worth. In this scenario, exchange does not necessarily take the form of a tug-of-war between two self-regarding parties, each seeking to give as little and gain as much as possible regardless of respective deserved praises. This kind of exchange, thus, goes beyond the idea of pure pursuit of one's own interest. One's own interest can include the interest of our neighbour (for example, when we exchange to provide food for our family) – but it does not take necessarily into account the interest of the other party in exchange (see Brown 1994, Fleischacker 2004a, Heath 2013). Instead, in the exchange based on just evaluation, respective interests are equally taken into account in order to reach their just balance, which reveals to us how much the others value our worth.

This balance does not necessarily result in the *moderation* of respective interests both parties have in obtain from exchange as much as possible, and which brings natural price to represent a sort of Aristotelian golden mean between them (as in Walraevens 2014, 424), but in the *just evaluation* of the respective interests both parties in exchange have in seeing their deserved praises rightly recognised.

According to Smith it is only by appealing to the evaluation of the impartial spectator that «we can ever make any proper comparison between our own interests and those of other people»

(TMS III.3.1). On the basis of this comparison, distinction can be made between just evaluation and the two traditional kinds of justice involved respectively in exchanging (just evaluation), stealing (commutative justice) and giving (distributive justice).

Smith sees generosity as distinct from «exquisite sympathy» in that it is not the pure and simple fruit of humanity, but the result of evaluation, weighing up one's own interest with another's: «We never are generous except when in some respect we prefer some other person to ourselves, and sacrifice some great and important interest of our own to an equal interest of a friend or of a superior» (TMS IV.2.10). On the other hand, explaining how it is possible to hurt someone for improper motives, Smith writes: «To disturb his happiness merely because it stands in the way of our own, to take from him what is of real use to him merely because it may be of equal or of more use to us, or to indulge, in this manner, at the expense of other people, the natural preference which every man has for his own happiness above that of other people, is what no impartial spectator can go along with» (TMS II.ii.2.1). Distributive justice in the sense of generosity implies an evaluation of interests such that we prefer the other's interest to our own, while commutative justice comes into play when we injure someone else because we put our own interest above his. Besides these two options, however, there is the possibility of balancing respective interests, as may happen in the case of exchange, in order to obtain a proper equivalence between our own interests and those of other people.

Through the equivalence attained by exchange all parties can recognise themselves as equal to the others and mutual respect is *obtained*.²⁵ Mutual respect can also be seen as *precondition* for exchange, which means preliminary recognition as equals and thus respect for the freedom and property of the others (see Fleischacker 2004a, 94, see also Griswold 2017, 158).

²⁵ In this case there is no need to assume that in primitive society individuals have to recognise one another as equals in advance in order to be able to exchange (see YOUNG 1997a); it is sufficient to assume that they recognise one another as equals thanks to the equivalence reached through mutual agreement in exchange.

In this case equality does not come into the exchange relationship itself, but as the result of commutative justice avoiding the relations of subordination that would prevent exchange (which is, rather, based on reciprocal persuasion, (see also Young 1997a, 57–70)).²⁶ However, exchange can also be seen as representing the moment when recognition as equals is *ratified* through consensual attainment of equality between respective deserved praises and thus by just evaluation, which can in this way describe the exchange relationship. In this case, on reaching agreement the exchangers recognise that their respective deserved praises are valued neither too little nor too much, given the circumstances in which they find themselves. As an outcome that can derive from a minimal form of respect of the other, the fact that no theft or defamation occurs does not imply recognition of that equality which, as also for Aristotle, is not a precondition but a result of exchange.

IN THE LIGHT OF ARISTOTLE'S THOUGHT

In his biography of Smith, Dugald Stewart observes that Smith considered his system so general as to be able to comprise all the previous theories (see Stewart 1980 [1795]), implying that he interpreted them through his own principles, as he also seems to have done with Aristotle (see also Vivenza 2010). Having explained the concept of «mediocrity» in Aristotle, Smith argues that it is not necessary to show in what way it corresponds «pretty

²⁶ Taking the same line, see also DARWALL (2006, 48), who states even more explicitly that «Exchange thus involves a reciprocal acknowledgment of norms that govern both parties and presupposes that both parties are mutually accountable, having an equal authority to complain, to resist coercion, and so on».

exactly» to his reflections on the appropriateness of conduct in TMS (VII.ii.1.12; see also Vivenza 2001, Hanley 2006).²⁷

While on the one hand, Smith interprets the traditional concepts of justice expounded by Plato in the *Republic* or Aristotle in the *Nicomachean Ethics* (NE) in his own way, i.e. beginning from his system, we can in turn quite reasonably do the reverse and read Smith's interpretation of exchange in WN in the light of Aristotelian thought on exchange. This does not mean, therefore, historiographically associating Smith with Scholastic thought on the just price, closely connected with distributive and commutative justice (in this respect, see Young and Gordon 1996; for a critique, see Salter 1997; see also Young 1997b). Rather, this means reading the above interpretation in the light of the «proportional reciprocity» that, according to Aristotle, applies in exchange, making particular reference to the analysis in the fifth chapter of the fifth book of NE (Berns 1994, 80–83; see also Pack 2010, 6; Crespo 2013, 105–6).²⁸

In NE, Aristotle starts from the following point: in exchange a particular sort of reciprocity occurs which does not appear to respond to either distributive or commutative justice alone (NE 1132 b 23-25).²⁹ According to the logic of distributive justice, something is not attributed

²⁷ On the concept of *medietas* in Smith, see also PAGANELLI (2003), BROADIE (2010). On this concept related to Aristotle and the idea of natural price in Smith, see WALRAEVENS (2014). On natural price and Aristotelian gravity, see ANDREWS (2014). For a critical point of view on Smith and the Aristotelian golden mean, see BEE and PAGANELLI (2019).

²⁸ Here “reciprocity” is not used in its contemporary meaning but translates what is called *antipeponthos* in Aristotle. On this translation see BERNS (1994, 82); see also AZZONI (2006), THEOCARAKIS (2008).

²⁹ Scholars often associate commutative justice and exchange referring to the Scholastic interpretation of Aristotle, according to which no one should be enriched at another's expense and thus the goods exchanged should be of equal value (see GORDLEY 1981, 1991, 2001). In this sense, their prices should recover costs incurred (see YOUNG 1997a) or at least not deviate greatly from the prices prevailing at the time (see KOSLOWSKI 2001, 186-9). On the Scholastic tradition and just price, see also YOUNG and GORDON 1996, YOUNG 1997a. On exchange in Aquinas, see SANTORI (2020).

to someone on the sole basis of what he has done, but also and above all in relation to what the others have done. In other words, it necessarily involves the heterogeneity of actors. Nor, however, does a pure and simple reciprocity which can be represented with an arithmetic principle of homogeneity, and so interchangeability of the terms of the relation (*katà isotèta*), seem to apply to the logic of commutative justice. Aristotle takes the example of an officer empowered to punish, who punishes by beating with no right to be beaten in return, in contrast with someone who strikes an officer and can not only be beaten in return but also, and more to the point, must be punished for having threatened the order personified by the officer (EN 1132 b 28-30).

In exchange, however, Aristotle observes, each receives in proportion to what one has given.³⁰ This proportion is just if the difference in worth between the peasant and a cobbler is proportioned to the different value of their work (EN 1133 a 12-14). Here we have a form of justice that is *similar* to distributive justice because it takes into account the differences between individuals but which *differs* from it since exchange does not involve distribution of unequal parts between unequal parties. Exchange implies the reciprocal distribution which takes the differences into account, albeit in such a way as to bring about equality between them; and the unequal parties give and receive parts that are equal in value. Nor is it a matter of commutative justice alone, which sees what has been taken from us given back to us. With exchange, in fact, no one expects to receive a shoe in exchange for a shoe, or bread for bread, but shoes of a value proportionally equal to that of the bread exchanged. In this sense, exchange according to Aristotle does not mean *re-establishing* an equality subsequent to the disparity resulting from some injury, but *establish* an equality through comparison between

³⁰ Here «proportion» translates what is called *analoghia* in Aristotle. On *analoghia* and the connected role of money in Aristotle, see AMATO (2015); see also BERTHOUD (2018). On the various ways in which Aristotle refers to exchange, see FANTACCI (2005).

respective worth. In this sense, equality is not the starting point to be reached anew but the point of arrival, the result of the exchange (see also Amato 2015, Berthoud 2018).

The principles of distributive and commutative justice are in play, but it is not basically a matter of either of them alone; what is in operation is a more comprehensive and extensive form of justice akin to the third kind indicated by Smith, namely the justice involved in every correct assessment of the value of objects of judgement.

In exchange as described by Aristotle, the differences are not treated in different ways as in the case of distributive justice, but are brought into equality, and this equalisation occurs in such a way that the initial differences are not rectified or annulled, as in the case of commutative justice, but on the contrary are recognised as such. In this way, as Aristotle observes, exchange allows a peasant to continue to be a peasant just as to a cobbler to continue to be a cobbler, without either having to do by oneself what one can obtain from the other (NE 1133 a-b). It is thanks to proportional reciprocity in exchange, according to Aristotle, that society holds and remains together (see also Berns 1994, 82–83).

From this point of view, what marks Smith out from Aristotle is his investigation into the origins of exchange. According to Smith, individuals do not exchange in consideration of the general advantages that the division of labour would give them, but out of a natural propensity to exchange (WN I.ii), which in this case is seen as the desire to obtain the deserved approval of the other. While Aristotle holds that without justice in exchange it would not be possible to have a society in which the division of labour prevails (NE 1133 b 5-7), Smith, for his part, seems to assert that such a society arises from the desire to reach an agreement on just evaluation by means of exchange.

From this perspective it can be read a passage in TMS often quoted by commentators in order to stress the difference between distributive and commutative justice for the viability of society (see, among others, Raphael 1973, Cropsey 1975, Haakonssen 1981, Calkins and

Werhane 1998, Fleischacker 2004a, Forman-Barzilai 2010, Otteson 2017). In this passage we can detect the presence of the third justice, too.

Smith argues that appropriate beneficence is «the ornament which embellishes» society, while commutative justice is «the main pillar that upholds the whole edifice» (TMS II.ii.3.4). When distributive justice is present in society in the form of gratitude, generosity and mutual love, then «society flourishes and is happy» (TMS II.ii.3.2). But it is commutative justice, in the form of fear of deserved punishment, that guards against the danger that «mutual resentment and animosity take place» and society «crumbles into atoms» (TMS II.ii.3.4).³¹

However, between these two extremes – between reciprocal injury which destroys society and reciprocal beneficence which enhances it – there is a third way of relating with one another, and it upholds society:

Though no man in it should owe any obligation, or be bound in gratitude to any other, it may still be upheld by a mercenary exchange of good offices *according to an agreed valuation*. (TMS II.ii.3.2, emphasis added)

Society can exist without distributive justice, but commutative justice alone cannot suffice: the need is for individuals to exchange good offices «according to an agreed valuation» (TMS II.ii.3.2). To agree on the evaluation of mutual good offices, without there being reciprocal generosity, the need is for that just evaluation that goes beyond mere recognition of the

³¹ Smith does not say that society exists merely when someone who hurts someone else is punished. He is much more precise, and says: «The very existence of society requires that *unmerited and unprovoked* malice should be restrained by *proper* punishments» (II.i.5.10, emphasis added). The fear of undeserved punishment might not affect the motivations of agents – in particular the most virtuous – who are set on performing actions which they in any case consider to be just. Reinforcing commutative justice there is not only the punishment set by the law, but above all the fear of coming in for a punishment which the impartial spectator would consider deserved (TMS II.ii.3.4).

property of the others. Even without theft or generosity, society could fail to take shape if it were not for «exchange of good offices according to an agreed valuation» (TMS II.ii.3.2). From the point of view of mere commutative justice, individuals could be just «by sitting still and doing nothing» (TMS II.ii.1.9; see also Vivenza 2001, 51). It is thanks to exchange of good offices, according to Smith, that society is upheld.

Commutative justice prevents the risk of society breaking up, but it is not what holds it together, being based on that unsocial sentiment which is resentment. Distributive justice embellishes society but does not lie at its foundation. Just evaluation can be considered that kind of justice which at the same time allows society to be viable thanks to exchange of good offices, not to break down, as commutative justice and, as distributive justice, to be embellished.

CONCLUSIONS

This article offers another possible path in explication of exchange than that based on self-interest and the absence of the traditional kinds of justice in the economic relation. In Smith's thought there is a third way to be unjust, which is not connected to commutative and distributive justice, but to just evaluation of worth by the impartial spectator. The two traditional kinds of justice imply just evaluation of merits and demerits, but they do not cover the whole domain in which just evaluation can apply. Apart from explaining rights that may be imposed by force, or give rise to generosity, just evaluation can also help us to explain exchange. Just evaluation in exchange allows us to reach that just equalization of worth which can entail the desired recognition of our worth. As in Aristotle, also in Smith exchange can be thus seen as an occasion for establishing equality between individuals, and not only as a possible outcome of pre-established equal relationships.

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